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D8.9 Standards & open-source plan and activities V1

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The **AI4PublicPolicy** Consortium consists of:

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2	STICHTING EGI	EGI	Netherlands		
3	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT	INTRA	Luxembourg		
4	SIA SPA	SIA	Italy		13/7/2022
5	NOVOTRADING LIMITED	NOVO	United Kingdom		
6	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	UNP	Portugal		
7	VILABS (CY) LTD	VIL	Cyprus		
8	ARTHUR'S LEGAL BV	ALBV	Netherlands		
9	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain		
10	DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS	DAEM	Greece		
11	COMUNE DI GENOVA	CDG	Italy		
12	LEFKOSIA MUNICIPALITY	NIC	Cyprus		
13	LISBOA E-NOVA - AGENCIA DE ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DE LISBOA	LIS	Portugal		
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Abbreviations

ACTE	Association Civic Tech Europe
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CAI	Committee on Artificial Intelligence
CDEP	Committee on Digital Economy Policy
CoE	Council of Europe
DO	Decision Ontology
EC	European Commission
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FitSM	Federated IT Service Management
GA	Grant Agreement
GCoM	Global Covenant of Mayors
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OWL	Web Ontology Language
SDO	Standards Development Organization
UCLG	United Cities and Local Governments
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Executive summary

Deliverable D8.9 is the outcome of T8.3 “Standardization and Policy Making Activities”. Its purpose is to document the identification of standards relevant to the project activities, the identification of sections of the project that may be brought into the standardization process, and the engagement of the AI4PP project partners with standardisation bodies or similar fora.

The standardization activities plan within AI4PP comprises of the following steps:

1. Identification of standards and regulations relevant to the project research activities, technologies and pilot cases. (documented in D2.2)
2. Identification of standards applicable to the project outcomes, and standardization bodies with high potential for collaboration.
3. Identification of technologies and outcomes of the project which are strongly related to and can contribute to existing standards and the work of Standards Development Organisations (SDOs).
4. Planning and implementation of specific actions aiming to collaboration with selected organizations and SDOs.
5. Continuous monitoring and update of standards, regulations and SDOs related to the project.
6. Exploitation of standardization activities and outcomes.

This is the first of two versions of this Deliverable, which focuses on the identification of relevant standards and standardization bodies and the relevant partners within the project consortium (Step 2 of the plan). Version 2 (to be delivered in M36 of the project) will present the outcomes of steps 3-6 of the methodology.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP8

WP8 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization” is the dissemination, communication, exploitation and standardization work package of the project, describing all the actions that will be

integrated to the project's 36-month dissemination and communication strategy. This work package aims at:

- Studying the external scenario for AI4PublicPolicy results, providing input and requirements related to market needs and trends and defining the market context for exploitation and positioning against competing solutions.
- Maximizing the impact of the project, aligning business opportunities and the roll-out of a credible business model with the technical and innovation activity.
- Assisting and complementing the technical development with the business perspective particularly, relating to future uptake and sustainability.
- Ensuring proper communication of AI4PublicPolicy outputs, outreach and stakeholder engagement and subsequently raising awareness to the scientific, industrial, and general public communities with the inclusion of three targeted workshops aimed at reinforcing user needs and their results.
- Following, contributing to, promoting and ensuring usage of the corresponding relevant standards, while supporting liaison and collaboration with other EC funded related initiatives.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

Deliverable D8.9 is the outcome of T8.3 "Standardization and Policy Making Activities". Its purpose is to document the identification of standards relevant to the project activities, the identification of sections of the project that may be brought into the standardization process, and the engagement of the AI4PP project partners with standardisation bodies or similar fora.

This is the first of two versions of this Deliverable, which focuses on the identification of relevant standards and standardization bodies. Version 2 (to be delivered in M36 of the project) will present the project outcomes brought into standardization and all the activities related to this goal.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D8.9 comprises of four chapters as follows:

- Chapter 1 is introductory, providing basic information about the AI4PP project, an overview of WP8, the purpose and scope of the deliverable and its structure.
- Chapter 2 presents the standardization plan.
- Chapter 3 presents a list of relevant standards and standardization bodies, as identified by the project partners on M24 of the project.
- Chapter 4 presents the next plans for T8.3 activities, which will lead to V2 of this Deliverable.

2 Standardization Activities Plan

The AI4PP project has strong commitment in following, contributing to, promoting and ensuring usage of relevant standards. The project will make use of various standards for semantic modelling and AI architectures/tools development, and in several cases will extend these standards, while documenting insights from their use in practical policy development contexts. The overall goal is that AI4PP will contribute to standardization work carried out by relevant bodies and SDOs (Standards Development Organizations).

Standardization activities in AI4PP have started early in the project, already in WP2, where a thorough analysis of relevant standards and regulations was conducted and reported in D2.2.

As mentioned in D2.2, *“standards are a repeatable, harmonised, agreed, and documented way of doing something. Standards contain technical specifications or other precise criteria designed to be used consistently as a rule, guideline, or definition. Standards are an important aspect of ensuring that products and services are delivered in a harmonised and consistent way, while providing consumers and users with the confidence that whatever products and services they are using deliver to specification.”* *“Regulations are rules made by a government or other authority in order to control the way something is done, or the way people behave”.*

The standardization activities plan within AI4PP comprises of the following steps:

1. **Identification of standards and regulations relevant** to the project research activities, technologies, and pilot cases.

This step sets the foundation for all standardization-related activities. It has been implemented with T2.2 and documented in D2.2, which provided a comprehensive list of Standards and Regulations potentially applicable to AI4PP pilots. The list was a suggestion that the pilots may or may not implement or may have already implemented. In total 63 standards and regulations were identified, relevant to the five pilot cases.

2. **Identification of standards applicable** to the project outcomes, and standardization bodies with high potential for collaboration.

This step follows-up from T2.2 activities and is part of T8.3. Its goal was to identify specific standardization bodies and other organizations with which collaborations with the AI4PP partners could be established. This step has also been implemented and its results are presented in the present deliverable (Chapter 3).

The list includes (a) standards and organizations focusing mainly on technological research and development, (b) organizations relevant to pilot cities for presenting and discussing their work within AI4PP, and (c) guidelines and regulations related to ethical AI.

3. **Identification of technologies and outcomes of the project** which are strongly related to and can contribute to existing standards and the work of SDOs.

Technical partners will bring into the standardization process parts of the project they believe could contribute to standards.

4. **Planning and implementation of specific actions** aiming to collaboration with selected organizations and SDOs.

Activities include establishing contact with the appropriate SDOs, proposing, and promoting the project outcomes and identifying synergies. To this end, dissemination and communication activities and material will enhance and facilitate the collaboration establishment.

5. **Continuous monitoring and update** of standards, regulations and SDOs related to the project.

Throughout the project all partners will be regularly monitoring the standardization landscape to update the list of potential collaborations.

6. Exploitation of standardization activities and outcomes.

Any successful outcomes of standardization efforts should also be documented as key exploitable outcomes of the project, also contributing to the sustainability of the project.

3 Overview of standards related to AI4PP

This chapter presents an overview of standards and standardization bodies related to the technologies tackled within AI4PP.

3.1 Big Data Value Association (BDVA)

(<https://www.bdva.eu/>)

The Big Data Value Association – BDVA, (from 2021, DAIRO - Data, AI and Robotics aisbl), is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with more than 230 members all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations.

BDVA/DAIRO focuses on enabling the digital transformation of the economy and society through Data and Artificial Intelligence by advancing in areas such as big data and AI technologies and services, data platforms and data spaces, Industrial AI, data-driven value creation, standardisation, and skills.

GFT, INTRA and UPM are members of BDVA.

Partner	Relevance to standard
GFT	Participation at the Smart Governance Task Force, which includes tasks associated with the development of AI architectures and algorithms for Digital Public Administration Use Cases. GFT plans to transfer AI4PP's results to AI systems and algorithms used in the Digital Public Sector.
INTRA	Boosting the adoption of AI4PP's results by the BDVA community.
UPM	Alignment of the AI4PP Platform Architecture to BDVA Reference Architecture and SRIA.

Table 1. Partners related to BDVA

3.2 FitSM

(<https://www.fitsm.eu/>)

FitSM is a lightweight standard for IT service management. It brings order and traceability with simple, practical support and provides a common conceptual and process model setting out realistic requirements.

Partner	Relevance to standard
EGI	EGI Foundation applies FitSM standard for daily service management and has most of staff members that are certified at the expert level for the FitSM standard. EGI holds ISO 9001:2015 and ISO/IEC 20000-1:2011 certifications.

Table 2. Partners related to FitSM

3.3 Association Civic Tech Europe (ACTE)

(<https://www.acte-europe.org/>)

Civic Tech aims to solve the crisis of the representativeness of modern democracies by developing innovative technological tools. The ACTE brings together all European civic tech organizations, companies and associations who wish to contribute usefully and pragmatically to the development of the sector and to maintain a constructive exchange with public authorities.

Partner	Relevance to standard
NOVO	NOVO will apply the inherent principles are inherent in the action of civic tech by putting citizens are at the heart of the process, serving the general interest, ensuring the constancy and continuity of democracy, and being transparent with users. NOVO will also take advantage of the network of civic tech companies on a European scale.

Table 3. Partners related to ACTE

3.4 ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 Internet of Things (IoT) and digital twin

(<https://www.iso.org/committee/6483279.html>)

Standardization in the area of IoT and digital twin:

1. Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization programme on the Internet of Things and related technologies, including Sensor Networks and Wearables technologies.
2. Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, ISO and other entities developing Internet of Things related applications.

Partner	Relevance to standard
UNP	AI4PP will seek to develop solutions that adhere to ISO/IEC standards in particular in respect to the Interoperability for Internet of Things systems (ISO/IEC 21823) and Trustworthiness in the Internet of Things (ISO/IEC 30149, ISO/IEC 30147). AI4PublicPolicy might be able to contribute to pre-standardisation activities related to Application Profiles and Use-Cases for the Public Administration domain.

Table 4. Partners related to ISO/IEC JTC

3.5 The Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI) (WG03)

(<https://aioti.eu/>)

AIOTI promotes, bridges, and collaborates in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society. They cooperate with other global regions to ensure removal of barriers to development of the IoT and Edge Computing market while preserving European values, including privacy and consumer protection.

The IoT Standardisation Working Group (WG03) is working to define a comprehensive IoT landscape and standardization framework, to identify common high-level IoT architecture and recommend how to achieve IoT Semantic interoperability.

Partner	Relevance to standard
UNP	AI4PublicPolicy will take advantage of the common high-level IoT architecture and IoT Semantic interoperability specifications and will also possibly contribute to pre-standardisation and specifications activities related to the use of IoT systems in the Public Administration domain (e.g. with domain IoT semantic models for Public Administration).

Table 5. Partners related to AIOTI

3.6 W3C / Decision Ontology (DO)

(<https://www.w3.org>)

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) is an international community that develops open standards to ensure the long-term growth of the Web.

The Decision Ontology (DO) provides basic means for describing decisions and decision-making. It is formalized in the Web Ontology Language (OWL). The current DO prototype is intended to evolve and be extended with additional features as the work on the decision format progresses, and consensus is reached in the community.

In general, there are two main usage scenarios for such a core DO:

- archiving current or historical decision-making processes and their outputs (data-driven use)
- outlining decision-making scenarios (patterns, templates) in order to provide guidelines for the decision-makers (normative use).

Combining these two approaches would enable confronting the normative descriptions with actual decision-making data and thus giving sophisticated means for analyzing archived decisions which could be particularly useful for validation purposes.

Partner	Relevance to standard
GFT, RB	AI4PublicPolicy will contribute to W3C insights on the practical use of the DO in AI-based analytics for policy development. It will also evolve and extend DO with features suitable for policy making.

Table 6. Partners related to W3C/DO

3.7 EOSC Data Standards

(<https://eosc-portal.eu/>)

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science. The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. This environment will operate under well-defined conditions to ensure trust and safeguard the public interest.

The EOSC enables a step change across scientific communities and research infrastructures towards

- seamless access
- FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) management
- reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced along the research life cycle (e.g., methods, software, and publications).

Partner	Relevance to standard
EGI, UNP	AI4PP will establish a two-way interaction with the EOSC Portal in terms of data standards: The project will adhere to the standards supported by EOSC for data registration and sharing, while it will also contribute new standards regarding the representation of policy related datasets (e.g., the EEPsA (Energy Efficiency Prediction Semantic Assistant) standard for energy data).

Table 7. Partners related to EOSC

3.8 GovStart, UK

(<https://www.public.io/govstartuk-2/>)

GovStart is a GovTech programme, run by PUBLIC and backed by the UK government, to help tech startups transform the public sector. It takes startups at different stages and in various sectors, working with products that have powerful public sector applications, and provides them with the tailored support, strategy and networks they need to succeed. It allows them to identify key public sector problems and trends, demystify the government sales cycle, and helps them to fit their product to public sector policy.

Partner	Relevance to standard
NOVO	NOVO will take advantage of the right combination of insight, strategy and networks provided by GovStart. NOVO will also utilize PUBLIC's in-house product and business development expertise, ensure data and cyber protection compliance, and participate in roundtables, meetings and pitch events with public sector buyers and decision-makers.

Table 8. Partners related to GovStart

3.9 CivTech Scotland, UK

(<https://civtech.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/C4/overview?mode=global>)

Part of the Scottish Government's Digital Directorate, CivTech® brings together public sector expertise and private sector creativity to solve real problems, develop new products and deliver better, faster and easier services for everyone. Central to the approach is co-production with the citizen. The CivTech approach is helping transform the public sector with technological innovation - delivering significant benefits to public services and producing genuine uplifts for the Scottish economy.

Partner	Relevance to standard
NOVO	NOVO will take advantage of CivTech's approach for developing better public sector services and products for which there is a proven market, as fast and effectively as possible, to deliver maximum benefit. NOVO will also leverage the existing networks and localized knowledge for successful market entry.

Table 9. Partners related to CivTech

3.10 G-Cloud framework

<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/g-cloud-suppliers-guide>

The Government Public Sector Cloud (G-Cloud) is a government initiative that provides a single catalog of services and enables public sector entities to purchase Cloud services from official providers through a Digital Marketplace. The initiative is aimed at the wider adoption of cloud computing in the public sector and is designed to provide a more efficient, competitive and cost-effective way of purchasing information systems and services.

Partner	Relevance to standard
NOVO	NOVO has been selected as an official provider of Cloud services and applications for the UK Public Sector, through the UK Government's G-Cloud 13 framework.

Partner	Relevance to standard
	<p>The Digital Marketplace again includes all NOVO's innovative digital solutions, which modernize municipal services and cover all the needs of a Municipality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controlled parking system and urban mobility • Citizen service and Request Management System • Consultation and Communication System with citizens • Electronic payments • Volunteer Management Systems

Table 10. Partners related to G-cloud

3.11 Covenant of Mayors initiative

(<https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/>)

The Covenant of Mayors initiative aims to engage and support cities and towns to commit to reaching the EU climate mitigation and adaptation targets. Cities and partners committed to the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy share a long-term vision to combat climate change, working towards a low-emission and climate-resilient future.

Data4Cities is GCoM's evidence-based foundational initiative to measure and manage cities and local governments' climate ambition and progress. The smart use of data – big and small – demonstrate how and why climate change is happening, inform local climate mitigation and adaptation strategies, and provide the evidence that governments, private sector partners, and citizens need to increase their support for local climate action.

Data4Cities lays the foundations for standardized data by streamlining – with consistency and transparency – how and what climate information from cities is collected, what data can be made available to support cities to act, alongside the mechanisms used to analyse this information.

Partner	Relevance to standard
DAEM, CDG, NIC, LIS, BUR	The initiative will be a forum for sharing experiences and best practices from AI4PP pilots that relate to energy efficiency and contribute to EU's new Green Deal.

Table 11. Partners related to GCoM

3.12 United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG)

(<https://www.uclg.org/>)

The World Organization of United Cities and Local Governments is the largest organization of local and regional governments in the world. UCLG, as a global network of cities and local, regional, and metropolitan governments and their associations, is committed to representing, defending, and amplifying the voices of local and regional governments.

UCLG supports international cooperation between cities and their associations, and facilitates programmes, networks and partnerships to build the capacities of local governments. It represents 5 billion people across the world.

Partner	Relevance to standard
NIC	The Nicosia Municipality will disseminate to UCLG best practices from the AI4PP project.

Table 12. Partners related to UCLG

3.13 Living-in.eu

(<https://living-in.eu>)

This is a network of cities and organization working towards the digital transformation in cities and communities. The signatories agree to the principles of a city-led citizen-centric approach at the EU level, of ethical and socially responsible access, of sharing and managing data and of developing interoperable digital platforms based on open standards and technical specifications, application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and shared data models.

The technical community in the network has a published guide on interoperability (<https://living-in.eu/groups/commitments/technical>).

Partner	Relevance to standard
BURGAS	BURGAS is a member of the network.

Table 13. Partners related to Living-in.eu

3.14 ETSI - European Telecommunications Standards Institute

(<https://www.etsi.org/>)

Experts of ALBV are involved in the privacy and security related tasks of ETSI Special Task Force STF 547: A coordinated approach for Security/Privacy and (Semantic) Interoperability of standardised IoT Platforms. The STF 547 provides a strong support to some of the European Commission policies in the domain of the Internet of Things (IoT). The essential objectives of the STF 547 are to identify available standards and – as importantly - best practices in its areas of work; to build a bridge for the potential designers / implementers of IoT systems; and to support their work by providing comprehensive material for information, teaching/learning and demonstration with a very practical usage and implementation perspective.

Partner	Relevance to standard
ALBV	The focus area of the earlier stated STF is of direct relevance for the scope of AI4PP and, thus, creates benefits for AI4PP. In particular, AI4PP can leverage on the recommendations addressed to all IoT stakeholders (e.g., manufacturers, software developers) that were produced in the context of the work of the STF and, possibly, further produce recommendations mirroring the exact scope of AI4PP project, also, in line with the Guidelines of the High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence.

Table 14. Partners related to ETSI

3.15 Overview of relevant standards and guidelines for Ethical AI

This section introduces some of the most relevant standards and guidelines regarding ‘ethical’ or ‘trustworthy’ AI developed in the last five years by international and European bodies.

Some of these frameworks have already been adopted by public and private organisation across the world, as well as formed the basis for additional (and ongoing) policy developments. For additional

analysis on the relevance of certain principles mentioned below, the Deliverable produced under WP1, Task T1.5 on “Ethical and Legal analysis” should be consulted.

In this overview, among the many standards and guidelines available, consideration is paid to some of the most representative and consequential guidelines produced by the UNESCO, OECD, Council of Europe and the European Union.

3.15.1 UNESCO Recommendations on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) has recently published recommendations on the ethics of artificial intelligence (UNESCO, 2021). This is a document drafted by an Ad Hoc Expert Group consisting of 24 AI specialists. This was followed by a public consultation process, and eventually, in November 2021, the document was adopted by UNESCO member states.

The values incorporated in the recommendations are the following. Firstly, it emphasises that AI should maintain ‘respect, protection and promotion of human rights and fundamental freedoms and human dignity’. Secondly, AI should promote and sustain an environment and ecosystem flourishing. Thirdly, AI should ensure diversity and inclusiveness. Finally, AI should participate in and enable peaceful, just and interconnected societies.

Furthermore, the document contains a set of ten principles. These are the principles of (1) proportionality and do no harm; (2) safety and security; (3) fairness and non-discrimination; (4) sustainability; (5) right to privacy, and data protection; (6) human oversight and determination; (7) transparency and explainability; (8) responsibility and accountability; (9) awareness and literacy; (10) multi-stakeholder and adaptive governance and collaboration.

3.15.2 OECD Principles on Artificial Intelligence

In May 2019, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) decided upon and published an overview of AI principles (OECD, 2019). Similar to the HLEG Ethics Guidelines, the OECD principles focus on ‘a human-centric approach to trustworthy AI’. This was the first governmental standard on AI, proposed by the Committee on Digital Economy Policy (CDEP).

The principles are split up into value-based principles and recommendations for policy makers. The five value-based principles are (1) inclusive growth, sustainable development and well-being; (2) human-centred values and fairness; (3) transparency and explainability; (4) robustness, security and safety; and (5) accountability. The recommendations for policy makers are focusing mostly on a digital economy and supporting policy measures.

All OECD countries have committed to the AI principles. Some non-OECD countries, such as Brazil, Singapore and Egypt, also adhered to the AI principles.

3.15.3 OECD Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector

The *Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector* (hereafter, ‘Good Practice Principles’) presented in this paper seek to shed light on the value and practical implications of data ethics in the public sector. They aim to support public officials in the implementation of data ethics in digital government projects, products, and services such that i) trust is placed at the core of their design and delivery and ii) public integrity is upheld through specific actions taken by governments, public organisations and, at a more granular level, public officials.

The document introduces 10 Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector, including a set of specific actions which can support their implementation:

(1) Manage data with integrity; (2) Be aware of and observe relevant government-wide arrangements for trustworthy data access, sharing and use; (3) Incorporate data ethical considerations into governmental, organisational and public sector decision-making processes. (4) Monitor and retain control over data inputs, in particular those used to inform the development and training of AI systems and adopt a risk-based approach to the automation of decisions (5) Be specific about the purpose of data use, especially in the case of personal data; (6) Define boundaries for data access,

sharing and use. (7) Be clear, inclusive and open; (8) Publish open data and source code; (9) Broaden individuals' and collectives' control over their data; (10) Be accountable and proactive in managing risks.

3.15.4 Council of Europe

At the time of writing this Deliverable, the Council of Europe (CoE) is working on a convention for [ethical] AI. This ongoing work is based on the Committee on Artificial Intelligence (CAI), mandated by the Committee of Ministers to elaborate a '[framework] Convention on the development, design and application of artificial intelligence, based on the Council of Europe's standards and that is conducive to innovation'.

At the moment, the new convention will be based on the work carried out, until December 2021, by the Council's Ad Hoc Committee on Artificial Intelligence (CAHAI). This work was presented under the title of "Possible elements of a legal framework on artificial intelligence, based on the Council of Europe's standards on human rights, democracy and the rule of law" (CAHI, 2021).

Besides, other standards and guidelines concerning the impacts of algorithmic systems on human rights as well as, more specifically, on personal data, have been developed.

The Recommendation on the 'human rights impact of algorithmic systems' (Council of Europe, 2020) contains guidelines to advise States, and public and private sector actors, in all their actions regarding the design, development and ongoing deployment of algorithmic systems.

Also relevant for AI4PublicPolicy are the guidelines concerning 'AI and [personal] data protection' (Council of Europe, 2019). The latter Guidelines provide a set of baseline measures that governments, AI developers, manufacturers, and service providers should follow to ensure that AI applications do not undermine the human dignity and the human rights and fundamental freedoms of every individual, in particular with regard to the right to data protection.

3.15.5 European Union – HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence

On 8 April 2019, the High-Level Expert Group on AI presented Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG, 2019). The AI HLEG group consists of experts appointed by the European Commission that provide advice on an AI strategy.

The overall work of the AI HLEG group can be considered central to the development of the Commission's approach to Artificial Intelligence. The concept of trustworthiness and the 7 key requirements, introduced by the Ethics Guidelines are guiding the upcoming legislative steps in AI (i.e., AI Act and AI Liability Directive).

The AI HLEG's recommendations have served as resources for policymaking initiatives taken by the Commission and its Member States. Among those initiatives, there was the Communication on Building Trust in Human Centric Artificial Intelligence, the White Paper on Artificial Intelligence: a European approach to excellence and trust and the updated Coordinated plan on AI.

AI HLEG's guidelines lay out a framework of four ethical principles: respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability. Moreover, seven key requirements that trustworthy AI systems are supposed to meet. The ethical principles are respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability.

The seven key requirements involve:

(1) human agency and oversight; (2) technical robustness and safety; (3) privacy and data governance; (4) transparency; (5) diversity, non-discrimination and fairness; (6) social and environmental wellbeing; and (7) accountability.

Moreover, the AI HLEG points out that there might be fundamental tensions between different principles and requirements. Therefore, it is good practice to continuously identify, evaluate, document and communicate these trade-offs and their solutions.

4 Next steps

D8.9 is the first version of two reports documenting the standardization efforts of the project partners. The second version will be delivered in M36 and will report on all related activities between months 24-36 of the project.

These activities are the next steps in the standardization plan, namely:

- Identification of technologies and outcomes of the project that can contribute to existing standards and to the work of SDOs.
- Planning and implementation of specific actions aiming to establish collaboration with selected organizations and SDOs.
- Continuous monitoring and update of standards, regulations and SDOs related to the project.
- Link to exploitation and sustainability work, aiming to exploit the outcomes of standardization activities.

5 References

- Council of Europe, 2019.
- Committee of Ministers, 2019. Declaration by the Committee of Ministers on the manipulative capabilities of algorithmic processes (Adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 13 February 2019 at the 1337th meeting of the Ministers' Deputies).
- Committee of Ministers, 2020. Recommendation CM/Rec(2020)1 of the Committee of Ministers to member States on the human rights impacts of algorithmic systems (Adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 8 April 2020 at the 1373rd meeting of the Ministers' Deputies).
- High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG, 2019). ETHICS GUIDELINES FOR TRUSTWORTHY AI. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>
- European Commission, 2019. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS – Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence. COM(2019) 168 final.
- European Commission, 2020. WHITE PAPER On Artificial Intelligence - A European approach to excellence and trust. COM(2020) 65 final.
- European Commission, 2021. COORDINATED PLAN ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE 2021 REVIEW. COM(2021) 205 final (ANNEX).
- OECD, AI Principles overview <https://oecd.ai/en/ai-principles>
- OECD, 2021. Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector.
- UNESCO, 2021. Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence. Adopted on 23 November 2021.